

The Relationship Between Calling and Burnout of Psychological Hotline Operators: Career Commitment as a Mediator

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Abstract

Background: Psychological hotlines have long been an important channel for public mental health support; however, the high intensity and stress of hotline work may lead to occupational burnout among operators. This study aimed to investigate the occupational burnout status of psychological hotline operators and explore the relationship between calling and occupational burnout, as well as the underlying mechanisms.

Methods: The study employed a mixed-methods approach. Qualitative research was conducted using purposive sampling, involving semi-structured interviews with 18 psychological hotline operators (94.4% female, mean age 31.28 ± 5.67 years, mean service duration 26.17 ± 23.46 months) to explore the causes of occupational burnout and motivations for joining the profession. Quantitative research involved a longitudinal survey, collecting data at three time points (T1, T2, T3) over a two-month period, with 159, 137, and 125 valid responses, respectively. Among T1 participants, 89.9% were female, with a mean age of 36.06 ± 9.53 years and an average service duration of 21.15 ± 25.16 months.

Results: calling was significantly associated with occupational burnout, but no lagged causal relationship was observed. There was a positive cross-lagged effect between calling and occupational commitment, with calling predicting an increase in occupational commitment, and occupational commitment further enhancing calling, with the latter showing stronger predictive power. These interactions were consistent over time. Although occupational commitment did not significantly predict occupational burnout, burnout significantly predicted a decrease in occupational commitment, and this effect persisted over time. Occupational commitment fully mediated the lagged effect of occupational burnout on calling.

Conclusions: The work experiences of psychological hotline operators significantly impact occupational commitment and calling, which in turn affect occupational burnout. Hotline institutions should implement comprehensive institutional safeguards, foster an open culture, and provide group interventions to prevent or mitigate operator burnout and enhance calling and professional identity.

Introduction

Psychological hotlines have always been an important channel for providing psychological support to the

public. However, hotline work is often accompanied by high-intensity emotional labor and psychological stress, making frontline operators prone to occupational

More Information

How to cite this article: Zhang W, Zhang Y, Zhuang M. The Relationship Between Calling and Burnout of Psychological Hotline Operators: Career Commitment as a Mediator. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(1):80-93.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(1).12

Keywords:

calling,
occupational burnout,
occupational commitment,
cross-lagged model.

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burnout. Occupational burnout is a syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment resulting from prolonged psychological stress [1]. It not only affects employees' job performance but can also have negative impacts on their mental health. Therefore, understanding the mechanisms of occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators, particularly the psychological factors involved, is of great importance for improving the efficiency of hotline work and protecting the mental and physical health of practitioners.

Calling, as a source of motivation at work, is considered to counteract the negative effects of occupational burnout. Studies have shown that individuals with a strong calling tend to have higher engagement in their work and are more likely to experience a sense of meaning and accomplishment in their profession [2]. calling can not only enhance job satisfaction and job performance but also strengthen occupational commitment, which refers to individuals' sustained engagement and willingness to dedicate themselves to their work over the long term [3]. However, existing research has not sufficiently explored how calling influences occupational burnout through occupational commitment, especially in specific work environments such as that of psychological hotline operators, where empirical evidence for this relationship is still lacking. Although some studies have examined the relationship between calling and occupational burnout, they have mainly focused on certain specific occupational groups, such as doctors, teachers, and nurses [4,5]. In the context of psychological hotline operators, research on calling is relatively scarce, and most studies have not conducted in-depth analyses of how calling indirectly affects occupational burnout through other variables, such as occupational commitment. Furthermore, many existing studies are cross-sectional in design, which prevents the examination of longitudinal relationships between variables and thus cannot clarify the causal pathways among calling, occupational commitment, and occupational burnout.

The aim of this study is to fill this gap. First, we conduct qualitative research to explore the occupational perceptions, motivations, and causes of occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators. Second, we use a quantitative longitudinal approach to further examine the temporal relationships among calling, occupational commitment, and occupational burnout. We hypothesize that there is a correlation between calling and occupational burnout, with occupational commitment serving as a mediator. Specifically, we hypothesize that calling can reduce occupational burnout by increasing occupational commitment levels, and in turn, occupational

commitment can enhance calling. Additionally, we hypothesize that occupational commitment has a negative effect on occupational burnout, meaning that higher levels of occupational commitment are associated with lower levels of burnout. This hypothesis is based on previous research highlighting the crucial role of occupational commitment in job performance and mental health [3,6], though further empirical research is needed to support this.

Through this study, we hope not only to deepen the understanding of occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators but also to provide empirical evidence for hotline institutions to formulate more effective management and support strategies to prevent and alleviate operator burnout, thereby improving their work efficiency and mental health.

Study 1: Qualitative Research on Occupational Burnout Among Psychological Hotline Operators

Research Objectives

Research on occupational burnout often adopts a bottom-up approach, starting from the work experiences of frontline practitioners to reveal sources of stress and coping mechanisms in their work. Psychological hotline operators, as frontline workers in a high-pressure environment, are often at risk of occupational burnout. Through interviews with operators, this study aims to gain an in-depth understanding of their experiences with occupational burnout, the underlying causes, coping strategies, as well as their perspectives on hotline work and career motivation. The qualitative data will guide the questionnaire design for subsequent quantitative research and explore the mediating variables in the effect of calling on occupational burnout.

Research Methods

Participants

This study used purposive sampling to select 18 hotline operators from different types of psychological hotline institutions for in-depth interviews. The participants included 1 male and 17 females, with ages ranging mainly from 20 to 40 years, and an average service duration of 26.17 months. The participants came from various hotline institutions, including universities, hospitals, government, social organizations, and psychological counseling institutions, covering both full-time and part-time work modes. The sample size for the qualitative study was determined based on the principle of data saturation, which was reached after 16 interviews, in line with qualitative research requirements.

Research Instruments

A semi-structured interview method was adopted to obtain rich qualitative data and provide participants with ample space for expression. The interview outline included four parts: participants' basic information, experiences of occupational burnout, subjective factors

affecting burnout, and motivations for joining the profession. The interviews were recorded in their entirety using recording devices and the transcribed content was coded and analyzed using NVivo 11 software. The inter-rater reliability between two raters was 86%.

Research Procedure

Before the formal interviews, the researchers conducted pilot interviews to optimize the formal interview outline. In the pilot interviews, participants provided detailed descriptions of their experiences with occupational burnout and perceptions of their work. Based on feedback from the pilot interviews, adjustments were made to the order of the basic information in the formal outline, and the definition of burnout was added, along with clarifications on the contexts and manifestations of burnout experiences. Questions regarding career motivation were also added.

Formal interviews were conducted with a total of 14 psychological hotline operators, with interview durations ranging from 30 to 50 minutes. The interviews were conducted via online voice calls and were recorded in their entirety with the consent of the participants. After the interviews, the recordings were

transcribed into electronic documents, and proofreading was performed to ensure accuracy and completeness of the information. Using NVivo 11 software, the researchers conducted categorical and contextual analyses on the transcribed data to present the participants' experiences with occupational burnout and their perceptions of work (Table 1 – Appendix).

Research Results

Occupational Burnout Experience of Psychological Hotline Operators

The interviewer explained the concept of occupational burnout to the participants: "Burnout is a persistent negative state caused by work, characterized primarily by emotional exhaustion, accompanied by reduced self-efficacy, decreased motivation, feelings of distress, and gradually displaying non-constructive attitudes and behaviors in the workplace." Participants were then asked whether they had experienced burnout based on this definition.

Among the 18 participants, only one (Participant N) reported not having experienced burnout. The contexts and manifestations of occupational burnout experienced by the other participants were coded and categorized, as shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Contexts of Participants' Occupational Burnout Experiences

Context	Codes	Participants
Work Time	Late-night/Early Morning Calls	A, D, F, H, M
Workload	High Call Volume	D, E, G, I, Q, R
	Crisis Calls	B, E, G, H, Q
	High Emotional Intensity of Callers	H, O, R
Caller Characteristics	Long Consecutive Shifts	G, M, P
	Narcissistic Traits	M, O
	Aggressive Behavior	H, M, O
	Harassment	C, L
Length of Employment	(No specific context)	B, J, K

The contexts in which participants experienced occupational burnout could be categorized into four types: work hours, workload, clients, and time in service. Regarding work hours, participants reported that receiving calls late at night or in the early morning disrupted their sleep patterns, leading to feelings of fatigue, irritability, and burnout. In terms of workload, participants mentioned that burnout was more likely to occur when there were a high volume of calls, extended shifts, highly intense emotional calls, or crisis calls. Concerning clients, different participants reported burnout when dealing with callers displaying narcissistic or aggressive characteristics or when receiving harassment calls. Additionally, some participants mentioned that burnout developed over time in their careers, for example, feeling less enthusiasm for the job after working for an extended period.

Participant: Sometimes, for example, when I have an overnight shift, and when a call comes in while I'm trying to sleep, I end up not sleeping well, and at that point, I may feel annoyed.

Interviewer: Do you usually feel this way during night shifts, or does it happen at other times as well?

Participant: It can happen at other times too, but it's most noticeable during night shifts. — Participant H (Male, 31 years old)

Interviewer: One aspect is the specific timing, but what kind of situations make you feel this way?

Participant: It was around 2016 or 2017. I had been working the hotline for some time, and the workload was particularly heavy. So, for a while, I had this feeling of not wanting to take calls or go to work. Also, during that time, I might have

received more crisis calls, and one of them was particularly critical and urgent, which resulted in some incidents afterward. So, my state wasn't

very good for a while after that. — Participant Q (Female, 32 years old)

Table 3: Manifestations of Participants' Occupational Burnout

Category	Codes	Participants
Negative Emotions	Negative emotions (fatigue, irritability, boredom, frustration, helplessness, etc.)	A, C, E, G, H, I, J, L, M, O, P, Q, R
	Reduced emotional response intensity or emotional detachment	A, D, G, H
Negative Emotional Attitudes	Reduced willingness to take calls	B, F, I, J, K, Q
	Reduced expectations	B, E, G
	Reduced sense of meaning	A, C, K
	Reduced self-efficacy	A, C, D, O, R
Non-Constructive Behaviors	Distracted attention	M
	Reduced responses	B, G, M
	Reduced exploration	B
	Reduced reflection	A, B, E

The manifestations of occupational burnout among participants were categorized into three types: negative emotions, negative emotional attitudes, and non-constructive behaviors. Negative emotions included feelings of fatigue, irritability, boredom, isolation, frustration, and powerlessness. In terms of negative emotional attitudes, participants reported resistance to incoming calls, reduced expectations for their work, diminished sense of meaning, and decreased self-efficacy. Manifestations of non-constructive behaviors included decreased attention during calls, reduced responsiveness, and less post-call reflection.

Participant: And then there are times when, in particularly challenging situations, if the caller's resources are truly limited, and it feels like there are many paths available but none of them work

for the caller, I also feel powerless, which leads to a similar feeling of burnout. — Participant F (Female, 29 years old)

Participant: Yes, later on, I felt it was more like a task, and I felt that the help provided by the hotline was actually quite limited. After working for a long time, you realize that the callers often call about the same issues repeatedly, and it's still the same things over and over again. But during the call, it's really difficult to help them make a change. I think this also contributes to feeling like the work doesn't have as much meaning as I initially expected. — Participant K (Female, 35 years old)

Factors Influencing Occupational Burnout Among Psychological Hotline Operators

Table 4: Factors Influencing Participants' Occupational Burnout

Factor Category	Codes	Participants
Institutional Management Factors	Work Environment	B, J
	Professional Learning	C, E, G, I, J
	Salary Level	B, E, K, Q
	Management Setup	C, E, G, H, O, Q
	Operating Hours	B, J
	Interpersonal Atmosphere	B, E, G, H, I, K
Work Content Factors	Workload	A, C, D, E, I, L, R
	Work Hours	A, D, F, L, M, P
	Characteristics of Work Targets	E, F, G, H, L, M, O, R
Work Subject Factors	Physical and Mental State	A, B, C, D, F, G, I, J, K, L, P, Q
	Life Stress	A, G, I, J, L

Participants subjectively identified three categories of factors influencing the development of occupational burnout: institutional management factors, work

content factors, and individual factors, as detailed in Table 4.

Among the institutional management factors, participants mentioned work environment,

professional learning, compensation level, management settings, and operating hours. In terms of work environment, well-equipped duty rooms, easy-to-use communication tools, and a mature hotline system help create a comfortable work environment, providing a more relaxed and stable work experience for operators.

Regarding work content, workload was directly related to the level of fatigue experienced by operators. A larger workload was more likely to place a physical and mental burden on operators, exacerbating burnout. Additionally, work hours, particularly night shifts or prolonged work hours, increased the level of fatigue and contributed to burnout over time. A reasonable schedule can help operators recover sufficiently in the face of demanding work.

The characteristics of clients also had an impact. Hotline operators deal with various types of callers, some of whom may display narcissistic, aggressive, or harassing behaviors. Handling these more challenging callers can increase operators' psychological stress and make burnout more likely.

For individual factors, the physical health and psychological state of operators were crucial influences on burnout. Operators in good physical and mental condition were better able to cope with the pressures and challenges of their work; conversely, poor physical and mental health made them more susceptible to burnout. Furthermore, personal stress in daily life, such as family, financial, or health issues, also affected work performance. Operators facing high levels of life stress were more likely to experience anxiety and fatigue, increasing the likelihood of occupational burnout.

Participant: So, I think on one hand, going to a fixed location to take hotline calls is better than doing it at home, because when you take calls at home, you never know when the phone will ring, and you also have your own things to take care of at home. You might need to cook or do other things, which makes it difficult. Especially when working from home, I feel the situation becomes even more chaotic. — Participant C (Female, 30-40 years old)

Participant: And the second thing is, regarding the two hotlines I mentioned earlier, the compensation they provide is quite different. When the compensation is lower, I feel a stronger sense of burnout. It's really when you're exhausted and also feeling underpaid that burnout becomes worse, and I feel less motivated to do the job. Higher compensation can balance or mitigate these feelings to some extent, and I think it's an external motivating factor. — Participant B (Female, 24 years old)

Occupational Perceptions of Psychological Hotline Operators

In this part of the interview, the interviewer asked participants how they viewed the profession of psychological hotline operators. The responses could be classified from two aspects: emotional tone and content. In terms of emotional tone, participants' responses could be divided into three types: positive, neutral, and negative. Regarding content, participants' responses could be divided into three aspects: the role of the operator, characteristics of the profession, and clients (i.e., callers), as detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: Occupational Perceptions of Psychological Hotline Operators by Participants

Category	Work Subject	Work Characteristics	Service Targets
Positive Statements	calling, self-fulfillment, value, meaning, sense of accomplishment, satisfaction, joy	Timeliness, convenience	Emotional improvement, providing support, offering/activating resources
Neutral Statements	Responsibility, challenge, training, seeing diversity, practicing mission	Anonymity, necessity	
Negative Statements	Burnout, loneliness, difficulty, stress		

Participant: At first, I thought it was useless, but now I think it is very useful.

Interviewer: How did this change happen?

Participant: Because many people call while crying, even in the middle of the night, and they are not professionals; they are really at their wits' end when they find you. And through the hotline, through your voice, you can provide them with some relaxation, activate their resources, and it really helps them a lot. There are even times when I've seen this myself—I've

only encountered a crisis twice, but I've also seen discussions in our group where some people didn't commit suicide because of a hotline call. I think that value is very significant, especially during a crisis. — Participant H (Male, 31 years old)

Participant: I think this job is very meaningful because I have personally experienced one or two times when I was in a really bad mood, and I called the hotline I work at. After talking with them, my emotions were relieved. Many of the

people who call the hotline may not have the financial means to access psychological counseling, and since the psychological hotline is free, we can sometimes provide them with some emotional support. Although it may not be as effective as psychological counseling in making a change, I think at that moment we can give them some warmth. So, I think this is still meaningful.

— Participant K (Female, 35 years old)

Career Motivations of Psychological Hotline Operators

The motivations for participants to engage in psychological hotline work can be divided into two categories based on their sources: personal internal

factors and social external factors, as detailed in Table 6. Personal internal factors refer to factors originating within the practitioners themselves that drive them to become hotline operators. These factors include helping others, professional learning and practice, earning income, entering or transitioning into the psychology industry, meeting like-minded peers, self-fulfillment, and preference for certain types of institutions or flexible work hours. Social external factors refer to social and environmental factors originating outside the practitioners themselves, such as work needs and organizational arrangements, life events, and environmental factors.

Table 6: Motivations for Participants to Engage in Psychological Hotline Work

Category	Codes	Participants
Personal Internal Factors	Helping others	A, B, D, G, N, Q, R
	Professional learning and practice	A, B, E, F, M, N
	Earning income	A, B, M, N
	Joining/transitioning to a new profession	C, I, O
	Meeting like-minded peers	A, R
	Self-actualization	G, H
	Preference for institutions/flexible work hours	D, G
Social External Factors	Job requirements/organizational arrangements	K, L
	Life events	O, Q
	Environmental factors	H, P

Participant: One of the reasons I chose this job is the long-term mission I mentioned (helping others), which is why I chose various kinds of work that involve interacting with people and doing public welfare. Before this, I would lead groups and support communities in need of listening, whenever such opportunities arose. — Participant G (Female, 34 years old)

Interviewer: Okay, you just mentioned that you were doing this work in a public welfare institution. What made you choose to work as a psychological hotline operator at the beginning?
Participant: At first, it was kind of forced. I was originally a school mental health teacher, but it was a requirement for the "Civilized City" initiative.

Interviewer: The "Civilized City" initiative?
Participant: Yes, and in our area, because there are very few full-time professional teachers, when a few organizations were jointly building an institution, it was required that qualified teachers take shifts at the institution. Otherwise, most school teachers would still be doing in-person counseling and school-related work on campus. So, this was how we all started, without initially intending to participate, as we didn't

even know about such an institution. Once we joined, it seemed quite novel, as it was related to our own professional expertise, and only then did we slowly start to learn more about it. — Participant L (Female, 32 years old)

Discussion

This study, through in-depth interviews with psychological hotline operators, revealed the contexts, manifestations, and multiple underlying causes of occupational burnout. Participants generally reported that feelings of burnout were particularly pronounced during late-night shifts, under high workloads, and when dealing with emotionally agitated or aggressive callers. Such burnout was not only characterized by low mood and non-constructive behaviors but was also closely related to physical and mental exhaustion. The relationship between high workload and emotional exhaustion has been supported by previous research, indicating that excessive work pressure can exacerbate mental health issues.

It is worth noting that psychological hotline operators, due to the unique nature of their work, experience relatively fewer interpersonal conflicts, which may be related to the characteristics of the profession and the high level of professional support they receive. The development of occupational burnout is influenced not

only by the work environment and work content but is also closely linked to the physical and mental state and life stress of the operators. Participants pointed out that stress and fatigue from daily life exacerbate burnout at work, which is consistent with previous research indicating that sleep disturbances predict occupational burnout.

At the same time, the occupational perceptions of psychological hotline operators also reflect their high recognition of their work. Although hotline work brings a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction, it is also accompanied by feelings of loneliness and stress. In addition, the motivations for becoming a hotline operator, as mentioned by participants, include helping others, self-fulfillment, and professional learning, among other factors. These motivations indicate that psychological hotline operators view their work not only as a means of livelihood but also as an important avenue for realizing personal value.

Study 2: Mediating Effect of Occupational Commitment Between calling and Occupational Burnout

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to quantitatively explore the relationship between calling and occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators. Based on the results of the qualitative study, this study also examines the mediating effect of occupational commitment between calling and occupational burnout. To overcome the limitations of cross-sectional data in causal inference, this study used repeated measures to obtain longitudinal data, thereby examining the causal relationships between variables [11].

Research Hypotheses

Based on the aforementioned context and previous research findings, the hypotheses for the quantitative research in this study are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There is a correlation between calling and occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators.

Hypothesis 2: Occupational commitment mediates the relationship between calling and occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators, as follows:

Hypothesis 2a: calling positively predicts the level of occupational commitment.

Hypothesis 2b: Occupational commitment positively predicts the level of calling.

Hypothesis 2c: Occupational commitment negatively predicts the level of occupational burnout.

Hypothesis 2d: calling negatively predicts the level of occupational burnout.

Research Methods

Participants

The study targeted psychological hotline operators currently working in psychological hotline institutions,

using online recruitment and questionnaire distribution. The first survey collected responses from 169 participants; after excluding questionnaires from ineligible institutions and those that failed attention checks, 159 valid questionnaires were retained (94.1%). The second survey collected 137 valid questionnaires (81.1%), and the third survey collected 125 valid questionnaires (74.0%).

The demographic characteristics of all valid participants were as follows: 16 males (10.1%) and 143 females (89.9%); average age of 36.06 ± 9.53 years; average work experience of 21.15 ± 25.16 months; education levels included 1 participant with high school or below (0.6%), 8 with an associate degree (5.0%), 71 with a bachelor's degree (44.7%), and 79 with a graduate degree or higher (49.7%). There were 27 full-time operators (17.0%) and 132 part-time operators (83.0%), representing a total of 22 psychological hotlines from universities, hospitals, government agencies, social organizations, and counseling institutions.

Research Instruments

(1) calling

The study used the 12-Calling Scale (12-CS) developed by [9] to measure calling. This scale defines calling as "a meaningful, passionate experience that people have in a particular field." The items on the 12-CS are domain-specific, and researchers can adapt keywords according to different professions. In this study, each item was modified to fit the characteristics of psychological hotline operators, such as "If I did not engage in hotline work, my sense of purpose would be greatly reduced." The scale uses a 7-point Likert scoring system (1 = "Strongly disagree," 7 = "Strongly agree"), with higher scores indicating a stronger calling as a hotline operator. The reliability of the scale ranged from 0.88 to 0.94 in studies conducted with groups from music, art, business, and management [9]. The reliability coefficients for the three measurements in this study are shown in Table 4.1, and this applies to all subsequent references.

(2) Occupational Commitment

The study used the Occupational Commitment Scale developed by [15] to measure participants' level of commitment to their profession or field. The scale consists of seven items, using a 5-point Likert scoring system (1 = "Strongly disagree," 5 = "Strongly agree"), with higher scores indicating higher occupational commitment as a hotline operator. Previous studies have reported good reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.83, 0.84$) and validity for this scale in various samples [15].

(3) Occupational Burnout

The study used the Chinese Professional Counselor Burnout Scale to measure occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators (An Qin et al., 2006). This scale is based on the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Service Survey (MBI-HSS), the Geldard Burnout

Inventory (GBI), and interview results. To adapt the scale for the target profession, each item was modified accordingly, such as "Since engaging in hotline work, I have become increasingly indifferent to callers" and "The hotline organization provides me with sufficient supervision." The scale includes 32 items in total, with 12 items measuring emotional stress, 9 items measuring reduced sense of accomplishment, 7 items measuring physical and mental fatigue, and 4 items measuring institutional support. A 7-point Likert scoring system is used (1 = "Strongly disagree," 7 = "Strongly agree"), with higher scores indicating higher levels of occupational burnout. The scale has demonstrated good reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$; An Qin et al., 2006).

Common Method Bias Testing

All data collected in this study were obtained through self-reported questionnaires, which could potentially lead to common method bias. To minimize this bias, a longitudinal design was adopted, and the questionnaires included reverse-scored items. In addition, the single-method latent factor approach was used to assess the impact of common method bias [13]. Exploratory single-factor analyses conducted at all three time points indicated no significant common method bias (T1: $\chi^2(1175) = 3742.642$, $p < .001$, CFI = .427, TLI = .403, RMSEA = .117, SRMR = .130; T2: $\chi^2(1175) = 3713.789$, $p < .001$, CFI = .413, TLI = .388, RMSEA = .126, SRMR = .147; T3: $\chi^2(1175) = 3716.976$, $p < .001$, CFI = .414, TLI = .389, RMSEA = .132, SRMR = .144).

Research Procedure

(1) Questionnaire Distribution and Collection

The questionnaire collection phase of this study lasted for two months, with data being collected at three time points: late January 2022 (T1), late February 2022 (T2), and late March 2022 (T3). During the first round, recruitment information and the questionnaire link were distributed via social media platforms to collect demographic information, data on various variables, and participants' contact information. The second and third rounds were distributed via the email addresses provided by participants. If participants did not respond

within two days after the questionnaires were sent, they were contacted via WeChat or text message to remind them to complete the questionnaire promptly. The second and third rounds only collected data from the scales and contact information. Data from the three rounds were matched using contact information.

(2) Data Processing and Analysis

During data processing and analysis, SPSS 22.0 was used for descriptive statistics and correlation analysis, while Mplus 8.3 [12] was used for cross-lagged model analysis.

Following the approach of [16] for analyzing mediation effects in longitudinal data, this study determined the final model by comparing the fit indices of the following four competing models (see Figure 1): stability model (Model 1), burnout-commitment-mission model (Model 2), mission-commitment-burnout model (Model 3), and interactive model (Model 4).

The stability model included only time stability (correlations of the same variable across different measurement time points) and simultaneous (correlations between different variables measured at the same time point) relationships. The burnout-commitment-mission model added a cross-lagged path from burnout to mission to the stability model. The mission-commitment-burnout model also built upon the stability model, adding a cross-lagged path from mission to burnout. Finally, the interactive model included both the cross-lagged path from burnout to mission and the cross-lagged path from mission to burnout.

The four competing models were compared using chi-square tests. Since all models included three waves of data collection, representing lagged effects between two different time points, lagged effects between T1 and T2 as well as between T2 and T3 could be examined. Additionally, considering participant attrition between time points, the study first used complete data for model comparison and determination, followed by using maximum likelihood estimation to impute missing data to validate the final model, in line with [14] recommendations.

Figure 1a: Model 1: Stability Model

Figure 1b: Model 2: Burnout-Commitment-Calling

Figure 1c: Model 3: Calling-Commitment-Burnout Model

Figure 1d: Model 4: Interaction Model

Research Results

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

The means, standard deviations, reliability coefficients of the measurement instruments, and correlation matrix for each variable are shown in Table 8. Cross-sectionally, at the same time point, calling and occupational commitment were significantly positively correlated, and both were significantly negatively correlated with occupational burnout. Longitudinally, correlations for the same variable were higher than correlations between different variables, but as the time interval increased, correlations for the same variable gradually decreased. Among different

variables, the correlation between calling and occupational commitment decreased as the time interval increased; however, the correlation between calling and occupational commitment at T3 with occupational burnout at T1 and T2 increased as the time interval increased. Table 4.1 shows that Hypothesis 1 is supported, indicating a correlation between calling and occupational burnout.

Cross-Lagged Model Testing of Mediating Effect

The researchers used Mplus 8.3 to evaluate the fit of the four competing models. Table 7 presents the fit indices and variance analysis results for the four models. The stability model (Model 1) included time

stability and simultaneous correlations. This model performed well in terms of relative fit indices (CFI and TFI), but the absolute fit index (RMSEA) indicated poor model fit, $\chi^2(18) = 77.438, p < .001, CFI = .949, TLI = .932, RMSEA = .163$. In Model 1, the significance levels for all stability coefficients were $p < .001$, with the lowest

stability coefficient being between T3 occupational commitment and T1 occupational commitment (0.277, $SD = .065$), and the highest stability coefficient being between T2 occupational burnout and T1 occupational burnout (0.901, $SD = .017$) (all reported coefficients are standardized values).

Table 7: Fit Indices and Variance Analysis Results for the Four Competing Models (n = 125)

	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI	TFI	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf
Model 1	77.438***	18	.163	.949	.906	-	-
Model 2	37.064**	15	.108	.981	.958	40.374***a	3
Model 3	60.377***	15	.156	.961	.914	17.061***a	3
Model 4	22.578*	12	.084	.991	.975	54.860***a	6
						14.486**b	3
						37.799***c	3
Model 4 (159)	22.829*	12	.075	.991	.975	-	-

Note:

1. RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; CFI = comparative fit index; TLI = Tucker-Lewis index.
2. a compares with Model 1; b compares with Model 2; c compares with Model 3.
3. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Next, the researchers tested the burnout-commitment-mission model (Model 2). This model added the lagged path from burnout to occupational commitment to mission, on top of the stability and simultaneous correlations. Model 2 showed a significantly better fit than Model 1, and all fit indices, except for RMSEA, indicated good model fit, $\chi^2(15) = 37.604, p < .01, CFI = .981, TLI = .958, RMSEA = .108, \Delta\chi^2(3) = 40.374, p < .001$.

Subsequently, the researchers tested the mission-commitment-burnout model (Model 3). This model added the lagged path from mission to occupational commitment to burnout, on top of the stability and simultaneous correlations. Compared to Model 1, Model 3 also showed significantly improved fit, but RMSEA still indicated poor model fit, $\chi^2(15) = 60.377, p < .001, CFI = .961, TLI = .914, RMSEA = .156, \Delta\chi^2(3) = 17.061, p < .001$.

Table 8: Means, Standard Deviations, Cronbach's α , and Correlation Matrix of Variables (n=125)

Time	Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
T1	1. Sense of Purpose	4.478	1.108	.917								
	2. Occupational Commitment	5.184	0.932	.685	.773							
	3. Occupational Burnout	2.799	0.751	-.343	-.617	.924						
T2	4. Sense of Purpose	4.489	1.077	.780	.691	-.335	.928					
	5. Occupational Commitment	5.138	0.958	.603	.776	-.605	.754	.790				
	6. Occupational Burnout	2.805	0.757	-.262	-.548	.902	-.328	-.558	.930			
T3	7. Sense of Purpose	4.544	1.069	.780	.662	-.355	.880	.695	-.327	.925		
	8. Occupational Commitment	5.086	0.974	.583	.744	-.631	.731	.849	-.586	.768	.825	
	9. Occupational Burnout	2.898	0.797	-.293	-.498	.867	-.351	-.547	.895	-.393	-.651	.937

Finally, the researchers tested the interactive model (Model 4). This model included both of the lagged paths from Models 2 and 3. The relative fit indices (CFI and TLI) indicated that Model 4 had a very good fit, and the absolute fit index (RMSEA) was close to an acceptable

range ($< .08$), $\chi^2(12) = 22.578, p < .05, CFI = .991, TLI = .975, RMSEA = .084$. Compared to Models 1, 2, and 3, Model 4 showed significantly improved fit ($\Delta\chi^2(6) = 54.860, p < .001; \Delta\chi^2(3) = 14.486, p < .01; \Delta\chi^2(3) = 37.799, p < .001$). Therefore, Model 4 was selected as

the final model to test the mediating effect (Hypothesis 2). When using maximum likelihood estimation to impute missing data, Model 4 was revalidated with 159 data points, $\chi^2(12) = 22.829$, $p < .05$, CFI = .991, TLI = .975, RMSEA = .075. Apart from the RMSEA indicator further improving to an acceptable range, the relative fit indices were the same as those obtained with the 125 data points.

The results of the final model are shown in Figure 2. Since the significance levels of the path coefficients for Model 4 validated with 159 data points were the same as those obtained with 125 data points, with only the path coefficients differing, the results presented in the text are based on the model obtained with 125 data points.

Figure 2: Final Model Diagram

Note: Only significant paths are presented in the figure, and all coefficients have been standardized. For simplicity of illustration, correlations between variables at the same time point are omitted, but these paths were included in the model analysis. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Final Model Results

The model results indicated that the autoregressive effects of each variable across time were significant, with regression coefficients ranging from .142 (SE = .062, $p < .05$; T1 occupational commitment to T3 occupational commitment) to .909 (SE = .028, $p < .001$; T1 occupational burnout to T2 occupational burnout). The model results supported Hypothesis 2a, indicating that calling positively predicted occupational commitment. This effect was observed between T1 and T2 (estimate = 0.197, SE = .052, $p < .001$) as well as between T2 and T3 (estimate = 0.188, SE = .051, $p < .001$). The model results also supported Hypothesis 2b, showing that occupational commitment positively predicted calling, with effects observed between T1 and T2 (estimate = 0.170, SE = .053, $p < .01$) and between T2 and T3 (estimate = 0.165, SE = .052, $p < .01$). However, no negative predictive effect of occupational commitment on occupational burnout was observed between T1 and T2 (estimate = 0.010, SE = .037, $p =$

.788) or between T2 and T3 (estimate = 0.009, SE = .035, $p = .788$). Therefore, the model results did not support Hypothesis 2c. Similarly, the second-order lag effect from calling to occupational burnout (i.e., the path from T1 calling to T3 occupational burnout) was not significant (estimate = -0.041, SE = .041, $p = .327$), and thus the model results did not support Hypothesis 2d. The model revealed an unexpected path, indicating that occupational burnout negatively predicted occupational commitment. This effect was observed between T1 and T2 (estimate = -0.196, SE = .041, $p < .001$) and between T2 and T3 (estimate = -0.196, SE = .040, $p < .001$). Based on this finding, the researchers tested the role of T2 occupational commitment in mediating the effect of T1 occupational burnout on T3 calling. The results indicated that T2 occupational commitment fully mediated the effect of T1 occupational burnout on T3 calling (estimate = -0.033, SE = .012, $p < .01$), with T1 occupational burnout negatively predicting T2 occupational commitment,

and T2 occupational commitment positively predicting T3 calling.

Discussion

Based on the results of the final model, several conclusions can be drawn. First, calling and occupational commitment were found to predict each other's growth, indicating a cross-lagged causal effect. This causal effect was consistent across time: from T1 to T2 and from T2 to T3, calling predicted increased levels of occupational commitment, and occupational commitment also predicted increased levels of calling. Second, occupational burnout was found to predict decreased levels of occupational commitment, with this causal effect being consistent across time: from T1 to T2 and from T2 to T3, occupational burnout predicted reduced levels of occupational commitment. Third, occupational commitment fully mediated the causal relationship between occupational burnout and calling. There was no direct causal effect between calling and occupational burnout; instead, the effect of T1 occupational burnout on T3 calling was fully mediated by T2 occupational commitment.

However, contrary to expectations, no predictive effect of occupational commitment on occupational burnout or of calling on occupational commitment was observed in the final model, which differs from previous research findings [7,8]. Three possible reasons are suggested for this discrepancy. First, there may be limitations with the measurement tools. Although the Chinese Professional Counselor Burnout Scale used in this study underwent a rigorous scale development process and demonstrated good psychometric properties, the unique characteristics of hotline work may differ from those of counseling and therapy work, meaning the tool may not accurately reflect burnout levels among hotline operators. Second, the relationship between occupational commitment and burnout may be influenced by other variables. In the WCT theoretical model proposed by [10] it is suggested that personality traits and psychological climate may moderate the relationships between calling, burnout, workaholism, and organizational exploitation. Third, the short time intervals in longitudinal data collection may have limited the observation of changes. In this study, data were collected at monthly intervals, which may be insufficient to capture changes in occupational burnout over a short period.

Conclusion

This study combined qualitative and quantitative research to explore the relationship between calling and occupational burnout among psychological hotline operators and tested the mediating effect of occupational commitment. The findings indicate that hotline operators generally perceive a sense of meaning and accomplishment in their work, but also face occupational burnout due to high job demands.

The qualitative study revealed that burnout among operators originates from multiple factors, including institutional management, work content, and individual physical and mental conditions. Burnout is particularly pronounced when operators work long hours, handle heavy workloads, or deal with aggressive or harassing callers. The quantitative study further revealed the dynamic relationships among calling, burnout, and occupational commitment, indicating that occupational commitment plays an important mediating role between calling and burnout.

The results show a reciprocal causal relationship between calling and occupational commitment, while occupational burnout influences operators' calling indirectly by affecting occupational commitment. This finding differs from prior research, which has mainly focused on the positive effect of occupational commitment on calling, while this study emphasizes the positive effect of calling on occupational commitment. Using a longitudinal design, the study reveals that negative work experiences not only directly lead to reduced occupational commitment, but also indirectly impact calling through occupational commitment, resulting in long-term negative effects on occupational identity and motivation.

These findings provide important practical implications for hotline management, as well as theoretical insights into the understanding of the relationship between calling and burnout. Through the lens of the dual-factor theory, the interaction between motivators and hygiene factors jointly affects operators' work motivation and occupational identity. The study suggests that hotline organizations should implement institutional safeguards, foster an open culture, and conduct regular group interventions to mitigate burnout and enhance operators' occupational identity and calling.

However, the study has some limitations. First, the imbalance in gender distribution among participants in the qualitative study limits the generalizability of the findings to male operators. Second, the short intervals in longitudinal data collection may have affected the comprehensiveness of the observations of variable changes over time. Future research could employ a longer-term longitudinal design, more detailed qualitative research, and multi-level analysis to further explore the relationship between occupational burnout and mental health among hotline operators, and could provide additional empirical support through intervention studies to address these issues.

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Table 1. Basic Information of Participants

ID	Gender	Age (years)	Education	Major	Occupation	Hotline Employment Type	Employment Duration (months)	Type of Hotline	Number of Hotline Organizations
A	Female	26	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Part-time	26	University	2
B	Female	24	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Part-time	26	University	2
C	Female	30-40	Graduate	Psychology	Freelancer (Counselor)	Volunteer/Part-time	18	University/Social Organization/Counseling Institution	3
D	Female	34	Graduate	Psychology	Counselor	Part-time	19	University	2
E	Female	26	Graduate	Psychology	Freelancer	Volunteer/Full-time/Part-time	32	Social Organization/Hospital/University	3
F	Female	29	Graduate	Psychology	Freelancer	Part-time	5	University	1
G	Female	34	Undergraduate	Non-Psychology	Freelancer (Consultant)	Part-time	20	University	1
H	Male	31	Undergraduate	Social Work	Social Worker	Volunteer	14	University/Hospital	2
I	Female	33	Undergraduate	Education	Hotline Operator	Part-time/Full-time	43	University/Hospital	2
J	Female	26	Graduate	Psychology	Freelancer (Counselor)	Part-time	9	University	1
K	Female	35	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Volunteer	6	Counseling Institution	1
L	Female	32	Graduate	Psychology	Hotline Management	Full-time	74	Government	1
M	Female	27	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Part-time	2	University	2
N	Female	28	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Part-time	2	University	1
O	Female	47	Undergraduate	Psychology	Freelancer	Part-time	65	University/Social Organization	2
P	Female	40	Graduate	Psychology	Counselor	Part-time	24	University	1
Q	Female	32	In-service Graduate	Psychology	Freelancer (Counselor)	Part-time/Full-time	75	University/Hospital	2
R	Female	27	Graduate Student	Psychology	Student	Part-time	11	University/Social Organization	2

